

FAMILIAL CONVENTIONALISM: EXTENT OF INFLUENCE IN CHOOSING A COURSE AMONG FRESHMAN STUDENTS OF FOUNDATION UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined the extent of influence of the family in choosing a course among freshman students of Foundation University. Given that there is already information established regarding parents' involvement in their children's education, there still is a minimal number of resources discussing specific variables such as parental involvement in career development for students entering college, and the extent of this influence in a student's college life. This study utilized the use of descriptive-correlational methods. The questionnaire was created with the use of Likert scale and interpreted through the use of Spearman's rank-order correlation and Kruskal-Wallis in testing the significant relationship between the variables. The respondents of the study were 153 freshmen students of Foundation University. This study revealed the extent of influence of the family on freshman students. According to the findings, freshmen students believed that familial conventional had a great influence on the courses that they had undertaken. And regardless of the extent of influence, data suggests that there is a significant relationship between the extent of effects of familial conventionalism and the students' perception on the effects. It was also found that a family's economic status is significant on how students perceive the effects of parental influence in choosing a college course.

Keywords: *parental influence, familial conventionalism, parental involvement, college course, career path*

INTRODUCTION

A family plays a huge role in nation-building. It may be considered as the basic unit of a society, but it carries the most responsibility in the progress of a community. This is where instilling culture takes place—the values passed down through generations are taught in a family. Another vital role of a family in the development of any nation is in the context of education. A family holds a crucial role in the educational process of a child. The expectations, influences, values taught, and overall parental involvement can be factors in the growth of young minds academically (Salac & Florida, 2022).

A study conducted in the United States by the University of Wisconsin-Madison, showed that no matter how fast the society advances, especially in the educational sector, one thing about families has not changed even a bit—the role of the family in the educational success of their children (Bogenschneider & Johnson, 2004). It may be true that in the US, adolescents are more of individualists in their way of living but in choosing a career path, they still often use their family situation as reference. A similar study conducted in Nigeria showed that parents have strong influence over the career decision-making process that their children undergo. Factors like moral values, educational level, and financial status of the parents play a huge role whether the influence will be positive or negative (Ekeng, 2022).

In the Philippines, families are known for having strong bonds and close family ties. Almost everything a Filipino does is for the family, even putting personal goals and ambitions aside. In a forum in 2021 conducted by DepEd, Secretary Leonor M. Briones stated, “Parents play a vital role in the success of the learners not only in the lessons they learn from the teachers, but also in the guidance to nurture holistically developed individuals.”. The government has continually imposed programs in both public and private schools to maintain the involvement of parents in education. Through DepEd Order No.13, s 2022 or the Omnibus Guidelines on the Regulation of Operations of the Parents-Teachers Associations (PTAs), the department ensures a stronger collaboration and a more important role for the PTA in the educational system of the country (Malipot, 2021).

With all this information already established regarding parents’ involvement in their children’s education, there still is a minimal number of resources discussing specific variables such as parental involvement in career development for students entering college, and the extent of this influence in a student’s college life. This is interesting knowing that Filipinos are known to have strong bonds with their family but still a lot can be explored regarding a family’s influence unto a child in terms of choosing a career.

The researchers wanted to know if familial conventionalism played a role in the lives of Foundation University freshmen students in deciding what course to take up and the extent of influence that parents have imposed towards them. This includes the variables that may affect the decision-making process of these students in picking their chosen courses. Results of this investigation will not only offer insights to parents on how

their influence can affect the future of their children, but also be beneficial to students who are about to make the decision of choosing a career path for the future.

Research Questions

1. To what extent does the following aspects of familial conventionalism affect freshman students in choosing their course based on:
 - 1.1. Duties and responsibilities;
 - 1.2. Cultural value;
 - 1.3. Perception of the course/career;
 - 1.4. Interest; and
 - 1.5. Differentiation of Self?

2. What is the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course based on:
 - 2.1 emotional status; and
 - 2.2 being obedience?

3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of effects of the aspects of familial conventionalism to the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course?

4. Is there a significant difference between the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course when they are grouped according to their profile based on:
 - 4.1. Course undertaken;
 4. 2 Family's economic status; and
 4. 3. Educational attainment of both parents?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research utilized the descriptive-correlational method. It is descriptive because it identified the (a) the aspects of familial conventionalism experienced by students, (b) the background of the students' families, and (c) describe the students' perception on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their college course. It is also correlational because the aforementioned variables were correlated. All the data gathered are presented through tables and interpreted for a better understanding of the readers.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in Foundation University Dumaguete City. The school is headed by a University President. The university president is supported by the Chancellors and Vice Chancellors who supervises the implementation of the Continuity and Contingency plans of the university. Under the Vice Chancellors for Academic Affairs are the twelve (12) academic unit heads or the Deans and Principals of the various colleges of Foundation University. Foundation University has two campuses, one for tertiary level and the other is for the primary and secondary level.

Research Participants

The respondents of this study were bonafide freshmen students of Foundation University of the Academic year 2022-2023 regardless of the academic program that they are currently enrolled in. In choosing the respondents, the researchers get the sample size using the Yamane's Formula. The distribution of the sample respondents are as follows:

College of Criminology	30
College of Nursing	84
College of Computer Studies	18
College of Education	27
College of Arts and Sciences	17
College of Hospitality Management	48
College of Business Administration	31
College of Agriculture	14
School of Industrial Engineering	<u>12</u>
Total:	281

Research Instrument

The major tool that was utilized in this study is a researcher-made questionnaire. The questionnaire is divided into two (2) parts.

Part I includes the profiles of the students based on the course undertaken, family's economic status, and educational attainment of both parents.

Part II concerns the extent the following aspects of familial conventionalism affect freshman students in choosing their course based on: (1) duties and responsibilities; (2) cultural value; (3) perception of the course/career; (4) interest; and (5) differentiation of Self.

To ensure the validity of the researcher-made questionnaire, the researcher consulted at least 3 experts in the field of instruction and pedagogy. The suggestions that they had provided were considered to ensure the improvement of the questionnaire. A dry run will be conducted to 30 students to identify the reliability of the instrument. This test was regarded as the most suitable type for survey research where items were not

scored right or wrong and where each item could have different answers. This will be calculated to verify the internal consistency reliability of the items. It is a measure of the extent to which all the variables vary from 0 to 1. Higher values of alpha are more desirable and a value 0.70 is considered acceptable.

Results of the dry-run on the effect of familial conventionalism yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.94 for Duties and responsibilities, 0.91 for Cultural value, 0.93 for Perception of the course/career, 0.92 for Interest, and 0.94 for Differentiation of Self. For overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course, the reliability coefficient was 0.87 for emotional status, and 0.82 for being obedience. The reliability coefficient of all values was 0.94 which means that items in all areas are reliable.

Data Gathering Procedure

Following the hearing for the design, the researchers worked on the corrections and suggestions given by the members of the interrogating panel. First, A letter of permission to conduct the study was sent to the deans of the different departments of Foundation University. After the endorsement of the letter of approval, the letter was presented to the teachers and respective respondents. The survey took place online with the use of Google forms in which the researchers have sent personal messages to students and shared links to teachers of Foundation University.

The results were then tallied using MS Excel and treated using a specific statistical tool generated via Jamovi Software, and was carefully analyzed and interpreted.

RESULTS

Table 1.1
The Extent of Influence of Familial Conventionalism on Freshman Students Based on Duties and Responsibilities.

Statement	wx	Verbal Descriptions	Extent of Influence
1. I perform well in scholastic activities to avoid disappointing my parents	4.29	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. I get my work done efficiently to make my parents proud.	4.16	Agree	High
3. I meet my parents' expectations on my efficiency in education.	3.96	Agree	High

4. I actively participate in class discussions because this is how my parents want me to perform in school.	3.90	Agree	High
5. I turn in my assignments on time to have additional time for studying as instructed by my parents.	3.83	Agree	High
Composite	3.98	Agree	High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Influence
	4.21 - 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 - 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 - 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 - 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 - 1.80	Strongly Agree	Very Low

As presented in Table 1.1, it can be noted that the overall composite weighted mean is 3.98 as classified as “high” extent of influence of the familial conventionalism based on the students’ duties and responsibilities. In the same data, it can be seen also that indicators stipulate those students performing the scholastic activities to avoid parents’ disappointment got the highest weighted mean of 4.29 or classified as “very high” extent of influence.

Furthermore, the remaining statements which include that they have done their work efficiently to make their parents proud, active involvement of the school activities, and submitted their assignments on time are classified as “high” extent of influence. This implies that students work their duties and responsibilities in school for their parents to be proud of them. The study is related to the study of Kazi and Akhlaq (2017), Factors Affecting Students' Career Choice, none of the respondents indicated the negative impact of family. They did, however, admit that when it came time to select and exercise influence while continuing to meet their commitments, their parents had conveyed their doubts and concerns.

Table 1.2
The Extent of Influence of Familial Conventionalism on Freshman Students Based on Cultural Value.

Statement	wx	Verbal Descriptions	Extent of Influence
1. I have to take a course that should lead me to be able to provide for my family when they get older.	4.41	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. I respect my parents because they know what’s best for me.	4.33	Strongly Agree	Very High

3. I follow my parent's decisions out of responsibility as their child	3.93	Agree	High
4. I believe that my parent's decisions will always supersede my own.	3.61	Agree	High
5. I choose my course out of a sense of duty to my family	3.59	Agree	High
Composite	3.98	Agree	High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Influence
	4.21 - 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 - 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 - 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 - 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 - 1.80	Strongly Agree	Very Low

Table 1.2 shows the extent of influence of familial conventionalism based on cultural values in choosing a course among freshman students which has a composite weighted mean of 3.98. Indicators such as students taking a course that should lead them to be able to provide for their family when they get older and students respect to their parents because they know what's best for them has a weighted mean of 4.41 and 4.33, respectively which indicates that the extent of influence of familial conventionalism is "very high."

Moreover, indicators such as students following their parents out of responsibility as their child, parent's decisions will always supersede their own, and choosing their course out of a sense of duty to my family are distinguished as "high" extent of familial influence. This data shows that students agree that cultural values as well as parent's decisions influence in choosing a course.

Table 1.3

The Extent of Influence of Familial Conventionalism on Freshman Students Based on Perception on the Course/Career.

Statement	wx	Verbal Descriptions	Extent of Influence
1. I know that I have chosen the right course because my parents also approved that course that I am undertaking.	4.33	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. I am fully aware of my direction in pursuing this course even if this is the choice of my family.	3.69	Agree	High

3. I am confident in my ability to succeed in my current course even if this is my parents' choice.	3.63	Agree	High
4. I know that obeying my parents' decisions to choose my course was appropriate.	3.61	Agree	High
5. I had never felt uncertain about my course even if this is the course that was influenced by my parents.	3.39	Moderately Agree	Moderate
Composite	3.98	Agree	High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Influence
	4.21 - 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 - 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 - 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 - 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 - 1.80	Strongly Agree	Very Low

In Table 1.3, it is presented that the overall composite weighted mean for the extent of influence of familial conventionalism on freshman students based on perception on the course/career is 3.98 which indicates a “high” extent of influence. The most significant indicator which has a weighted mean of 4.33 that has a very high extent of influence is that students believe that they have chosen the right course that they are undertaking because their parents has approved of it.

However, the statements of students being fully aware of the direction in pursuing their course, confident in their ability to succeed, and obeying their parents' decision to choose their course was appropriate has a “high” extent of influence. The lowest weighted mean at 3.39 where students moderately agree that they have not felt uncertain about their course despite being influenced by their parents. This implies that students value the involvement of significant others, like their parents or other family members, during their career decision-making process.

Table 1.4

The Extent of Influence of Familial Conventionalism on Freshman Students Based on Interest.

Statement	wx	Verbal Descriptions	Extent of Influence
1. I was the one who chose my course with the guidance of my parents.	4.35	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. I had communicated with my parents in choosing my course.	4.35	Strongly Agree	Very High

3. I had taken my course because it interests me as well as my parents.	4.30	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. I feel responsible for choosing my course because this was both agreed by me and my parents.	4.33	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. I choose my career because I have family members with the same degree/career path.	3.41	Agree	High
Composite	4.15	Agree	High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Influence
	4.21 - 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 - 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 - 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 - 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 - 1.80	Strongly Agree	Very Low

Table 1.4 shows the extent of influence of familial conventionalism on freshman students based on interest has an overall weighted mean of 4.15 which is classified as “high” extent of influence. It can be seen also that freshmen students strongly agree that they were able to choose their course with the guidance and proper communication with their parents with the weighted mean of 4.35 for both statements.

The statements such as students have taken their course because it interests them and they feel responsible in choosing their course because this was both agreed by their parents has a “very high” extent of influence. In the statements, the lowest weighted mean is 3.41. The students agree that in choosing a degree or career, familial influence or having family members of the same career affects their decisions. All in all, parental influence affects the interest of students in choosing a course in higher education.

Table 1. 5

The Extent of Influence of Familial Conventionalism on Freshman Students Based on Differentiation of Self.

Statement	wx	Verbal Descriptions	Extent of Influence
1. I look for my family’s advice when I have to make important decisions in my life.	4.11	Agree	High
2. I am aware of my strengths and weaknesses, and it aligns with the career my parents want for me.	4.04	Agree	High
3. I have my own identity but I still went with what my parents want for me.	3.16	Moderately Agree	Moderate

4. I have not yet found my purpose in life so I went with what my parents want because they know better	3.03	Moderately Agree	Moderate
5. I'd rather choose a different career based on my own purpose if only it weren't because of my parents' decision.	2.97	Moderately Agree	Moderate
Composite	3.46	Agree	High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Influence
	4.21 - 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 - 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 - 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 - 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 - 1.80	Strongly Agree	Very Low

The data in table 1.5 shows the extent of influence of familial conventionalism on freshman students based on differentiation of self with an overall composite weighted mean of 3.46 which is classified as “high” extent of influence. Students agree that they turn to their parents for advice when making life-changing decisions as presented in the first indicator with a “high” extent of influence.

Furthermore, for the indicators where students have their own identity but still follow their parents' decision, they have not yet found their purpose, and on choosing a different career based on their own purpose if only it was not because of their parent's decision all has a “moderate” extent of influence. This implies that there is a disconnect between some students in their desired career path and their chosen career path.

Table 2.1
Overall Perception of Students on the Effects of Familial Conventionalism in Choosing their Course based on Emotional Status.

Statement	wx	Verbal Descriptions	Extent of Influence
1. I have no regrets when it comes to the course that I am currently taking up because my parents approved it.	4.14	Agree	High
2. I believe that my college course is aligned with what my purpose in life is and I have my parents to thank for that	4.09	Agree	High
3. I believe that I can succeed in life through the course that I am taking up which my parents had great influence on.	4.07	Agree	High

4. I feel completely happy of where I am academically and a huge part of it is my parents' influence.	3.95	Agree	High
5. I feel like I am exactly where I am supposed to be academically because my parents had a huge influence on it	3.87	Agree	High
Composite	4.02	Agree	High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Influence
	4.21 - 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 - 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 - 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 - 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 - 1.80	Strongly Agree	Very Low

The Table 2.1 shows the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course based on emotional status and it has a composite weighted mean of 4.02 which is classified as “high” extent of influence. The factor with the highest extent of influence and has a weighted mean of 4.14 is that which students say they don't have any regrets with their chosen course due to their parent's approval.

On the other hand, the remaining indicators such as students believing that their college course is aligned with their purpose in life, and the influence and support of their parents in choosing their course and this affects their performance in school all have a “high” extent of influence. This implies that expectations can come from both parents and their children.

Table 2.2
Overall Perception of Students on the Effects of Familial Conventionalism in Choosing their Course based on Obedience

Statement	wx	Verbal Descriptions	Extent of Influence
1. I respect the regulations set by my parents that led me to my current course.	4.19	Agree	High
2. I heed my parents' guidance regarding the course that I am taking for conformity.	3.94	Agree	High
3. I believe that it is my duty to follow the decisions they make when it comes to my studies.	3.89	Agree	High

4. I am compelled to follow my parents' decision for my education because they pay for it.	3.80	Agree	High
5. I act in accordance with the course that my parents arranged for me to have their full support.	3.78	Agree	High
Composite	3.92	Agree	High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Influence
	4.21 - 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 - 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 - 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
	1.81 - 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 - 1.80	Strongly Agree	Very Low

As presented in Table 2.2, this shows the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course based on obedience which has an overall composite weighted mean of 3.92 and is classified as “high” extent of influence. The highest weighted mean is at 4.19 and shows that students respect the regulations set which led them to choosing their current course.

For the remaining indicators such as asking for parent’s guidance, following their parents’ decision when it comes to their studies, and acting in accordance with the course that their parents arranged for them, this all has a “high” extent of influence for the students. From this, we can conclude that obedience or being obedient to their parents has a high influence on their course/career preferences.

Table 3
Correlation between the extent of effects of the aspects of familial conventionalism to the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course.

Variables Correlated to the Overall Perception of Students	Computed r_s	p-value	Decision	Remark
Duties and Responsibilities	0.5752 (strong)	0.000	Reject H_0	Significant
Cultural Value	0.5212 (strong)	0.000	Reject H_0	Significant
Perception of the Course/Career	0.6221 (strong)	0.0045	Reject H_0	Significant
Interest	0.5018 (strong)	0.000	Reject H_0	Significant

Differentiation of Self	0.4984 (moderate)	0.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
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level of significance = 0.05 and 151 degrees of freedom

Value of r		Strength of Relationship
Between ± 0.50 to ± 1.00		± strong relationship
Between ± 0.30 to ± 0.49		± moderate relationship
Between ± 0.10 to ± 0.29		± weak relationship
Between ± 0.01 to ± 0.09		± very weak relationship

Table 3 presents the correlation between the extent of effects of the aspects of familial conventionalism to the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course. Using the Spearman Rank Order Correlation, the result shows that the p-values (0.000 and 0.0045) of the variables are less than the level of significance (0.05), thus the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant and strong relationship between the extent of effects of the aspects of familial conventionalism to the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course. It indicates that there is a large and strong link between what a person does or works on and what their immediate environment or nature informs him or her about what is ethical.

Familial conventionalism became a role in student selection. This indicates the significance familial conventionalism is instilling in an individual and creating a value and a standard for him as ethical. Subsequently, the study found that the factors that follow, Duties and Responsibilities, Cultural Value, Perception of the Course/Career, Differentiation of Self, and Interest, have a significant influence on how an individual determines what to do and what path to pursue. According to the findings, familial conventionalism became a selection factor for students.

Table 4.1

Correlation of significant difference between the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course when they are grouped according to their profile based on course undertaken

College Department	n	Mean Rank	Median	H	p-value	Decision	Remark
College of Education	32	76.2	4.00	1.25	0.8698	Fail to Reject H ₀	Not Significant
College of Agriculture	12	89.2	4.05				
College of Arts and Sciences And College of Business	22	74.7	3.80				

Administration							
College of Criminology And School of Industrial Engineering	19	80.6	4.00				
College of Nursing And College of Hospitality Management	68	74.9	4.00				

level of significance = 0.05

Table 4.1 presents the data in analyzing the difference between the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course when they are grouped according to their profile based on course undertaken. Using Kruskal Wallis Test, it reveals that there is no significant difference between the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course when they are grouped according to course undertaken ($H=1.25$; $p\text{-value}>0.05$).

On the other hand, there is a very weak relationship between the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course when they are grouped according to their profile based on course undertaken. Continuing the investigation connection between the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course when they are grouped according to their profile based on course undertaken. The study by Kazi and Akhlaq (2017) titled Factors Affecting Students' Career Choice found that more than half (56%) of the respondents to the present survey were interested in a career in dentistry.

These data show that, unlike prior studies, there is only an insignificant relationship between the factors. Based on their familial norms, the students' general assessment of their course is only minimal

Table 4.2

Correlation of significant difference between the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course when they are grouped according to their profile based on their family's economic status

Family's Monthly Income	n	Mean Rank	Median	H	p-values	Decision	Remark
(1) Below P15,000	54	85.4	4.15	11.57	0.0029	Reject H ₀	Significant
(2) P15,000 - P40,000	65	62.9	3.80				
(3) Above P40,000	34	90.5	4.05				
Post Hoc Analysis Using Mann-Whitney U Test with Bonferroni Correction (0.05/3 = 0.017) Below P15,000 vs P15,000 - P40,000: p-value= 0.0069 (Significant) Below P15,000 vs Above P40,000: p-value= 0.6599 (Not Significant) P15,000 - P40,000 vs Above P40,000: p-value= 0.0027 (Significant)							

level of significance = 0.05

Table 4.2 presents the data in analyzing the difference between the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course when they are grouped according to their profile based on their family's economic status. The data reveal that the p-value (0.0029) is less than the level of significance (0.05). This finding allows rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that a significant difference exists among the three groups. To test which group has higher perception than the other, a post hoc analysis is applied using Mann-Whitney U Test with a Bonferroni correction applied. The results of the post hoc analysis wherein the Bonferroni correction is applied with an adjusted level of significance of 0.017 reveals that (a) Group 1 has higher perception than Group 2; (b) Group 3 has higher perception than Group 2; and (c) Group 1 has the same level of perception with Group 3.

According to Alvarado, Adriana & Stewart Ambo, Theresa. (2020), high-income students outperform other students regardless of their level of entrance, with 91.3% finishing their degrees in that time frame compared to 88% of middle-income students and 83.1% of low-income students. This means that when an individual makes a decision, it is also influenced by their assessment of their own and their family's financial situation. The study discovered that an individual uses to envision things depending on what they

believe they can do, and that if an individual comes from a wealthy household, their vision would be quite different from that of an individual from a low-income family.

The study indicates that a family's financial condition is not just considered while making decisions, but it is also connected to how parents use it as a reason for encouraging their children to seek high-paying occupations

Table 4.3.1

Correlation of significant difference between the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course when they are grouped according to their profile based on the educational attainment of father

Educational Attainment of Father	n	Mean Rank	Median	H	p-values	Decision	Remark
Elementary Undergraduate	6	93.5	4.20	8.06	0.0894	Fail to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Elementary Graduate And Highschool Undergraduate	15	98.3	4.40				
Highschool Graduate	37	65.3	3.80				
College Undergraduate	28	69.6	3.85				
College Graduate	67	80.3	4.00				

level of significance = 0.05

Table 4.3.1 in the previous page presents the data in analyzing the difference between the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course when they are grouped according to their profile based on their profile based on the educational attainment of their father. The data reveal that the p-value (0.0894) is greater than the level of significance (0.05). This finding does not allow the rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that there is no significant difference between the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course when they are grouped according to their profile based on their profile based on the educational attainment of their father.

Parental influence can change one's perspective, or how a person comprehends or perceives the events going on around them. A student's profession might truly be influenced by their parents. Previous study indicates that the influence of the job or the educational attainment of the parents can be a big factor to the choice of an individual. Continuing the investigation connection between the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course when they are grouped according to their profile based on the educational attainment of their father these data show that, unlike prior studies, there is only an insignificant relationship between the factors.

Table 4.3.2

Correlation of significant difference between the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course when they are grouped according to their profile based on the educational attainment of mother

Educational Attainment of Mother	n	Mean Rank	Median	H	p-value	Decision	Remark
Elementary Undergraduate	3	85.2	4.3	6.63	0.1738	Fail to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Elementary Graduate And Highschool Undergraduate	16	93.6	4.35				
Highschool Graduate	29	75.8	4				
College Undergraduate	25	59.7	3.7				
College Graduate	80	79.2	4				

level of significance = 0.05

Table 4.3.2 presents the data in analyzing the difference between the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course when they are grouped according to their profile based on their profile based on the educational attainment of their mother. The data reveal that the p-value (0.1738) is greater than the level of significance (0.05). This finding does not allow the rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that there is no significant difference between the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course when they are grouped according to their profile based on their profile based on the educational attainment of their mother.

The study states that there is no significant difference between the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course when they are grouped according to their profile based on the educational attainment of their mother.

DISCUSSION

The result has shown that for aspects like duties and responsibilities, cultural value, perception of the course, interest, and differentiation of self, freshman students at Foundation University believe that familial conventionalism has had a great influence on how they chose their respective college courses. The study is related to the study of Kazi and Akhlaq (2017), Factors Affecting Students' Career Choice, none of the respondents indicated the negative impact of family. They did, however, admit that when it came time to select and exercise influence while continuing to meet their commitments, their parents had conveyed their doubts and concerns.

The data obtained revealed students' general perceptions on the effects of familial conventionalism. According to the study, emotional status and obedience connect to high parental influence, indicating that students are content with where they are in their careers, particularly if their parents have a strong influence over their decisions. According to PDP (2022), these intersections aren't the only factor impacting how people move towards the future; there's also a link between the past and the present. Family is regarded as a conviction and an ideal that serves as the basis for people's decisions.

The degree of the impacts of the features of family conventionalism on the overall view of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course has a significant link. This means that numerous factors influence students' perceptions of how they see and select courses. Students assess their culture, responsibilities, perspective of a certain vocation, personal distinctiveness, and interest as these elements are influenced by their parents. This proves that familial customs do have an impact on an individual's viewpoint. Not just internal or personal elements affect perception. External factors on perception can include what others think of us, their expectations of us, and cultural norms like taboos or social conventions (HARAPPA, 2021).

The correlation of a significant difference between the overall perception of students on the effects of familial conventionalism in choosing their course when they are grouped according to their profile based on both parents' educational attainment, family's economic status, and course undertaken is demonstrated. The findings reveal that educational attainment of mother, educational attainment of father, and courses taken have no significant impact in the general view of foundation university freshman students in terms of how they take their careers. In contrast, the study discovers a considerable difference between the three groups based on the economic situation of the family. In this regard, the study of Alvarado, Adriana, and Stewart Ambo, Theresa (2020) demonstrates that a family's financial situation is not only considered when making decisions, but is also related to how parents use it as justification for encouraging their children to pursue high-paying careers.

Conclusions

The results of the data collected have shown that most of the freshmen students believe that there is great familial influence on all aspects presented in the survey. These aspects being, their duties and responsibilities, cultural values, perception of the course, interest and differentiation of the self. Data shows that there is a high extent of influence across all aspects aforementioned. In terms of familial conventionalism based on emotional status and obedience, the results also show a high extent of influence from both aspects. Though there is an identified high extent of influence in terms of familial conventionalism in choice of course, the data does not show that there is a relationship between students' perception when group according to course taken. When looking into another factor external to the students such as their parents' educational attainment, there is also no significant relationship in course decision-making. However, there was an identified relationship between their perception of familial conventionalism when taking into consideration their family's economic status. This shows that students, or young adults in general, do take into consideration the perceptions and expectations of those they consider significant figures in their life and even have them be part of the decision-making process for things as important as career choice.

As the researchers gathered the data and thoroughly discussed it, they had found that studies with similar topics will be useful in addressing the gaps in knowledge and understanding about the extent of influence that the family has on their children in terms of choosing their courses in college. There is significance in making sure that students have clarity in terms of the course they are willing to pursue and the factors that affect this. On this basis, future studies can further examine the effects of familial conventionalism on a broader sample population and try to see if there is a change in perception based on other factors not included in the current study.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings, here are some **recommendations** for educational institutions and policymakers:

1. **Parental Engagement and Guidance:**
 - **Workshops for Parents:** Organize workshops or information sessions for parents to understand the impact of their influence on students' career choices. Educate parents about the importance of supportive guidance without undue pressure.
 - **Parent-Teacher Collaboration:** Encourage open communication between parents and teachers. Teachers can provide insights into various career paths and help parents understand the changing landscape of education and professions.
2. **Career Counseling Programs:**
 - **Early Exposure:** Start career counseling early, even before college. Provide students with exposure to various career options, internships, and industry visits.
 - **Individualized Counseling:** Tailor counseling sessions to individual student needs. Address their interests, strengths, and aspirations.
3. **Holistic Decision-Making:**
 - **Beyond Familial Influence:** Encourage students to consider multiple factors beyond familial influence. These may include personal interests, aptitudes, values, and societal needs.
 - **Self-Reflection:** Help students reflect on their own motivations and passions. What excites them? What aligns with their long-term goals?
4. **Curriculum Enhancement:**
 - **Career Exploration Courses:** Integrate career exploration courses into the curriculum. These courses can introduce students to different industries, job profiles, and skill requirements.
 - **Soft Skills Development:** Emphasize soft skills (communication, adaptability, problem-solving) alongside technical knowledge. These skills are transferable across careers.
5. **Peer Influence and Support:**
 - **Peer Discussions:** Facilitate peer discussions about career choices. Students can learn from each other's experiences and perspectives.
 - **Student Ambassadors:** Appoint student ambassadors who can share their career journeys and provide guidance to peers.
6. **Awareness of External Factors:**
 - **Media Literacy:** Teach students critical media analysis. Help them recognize stereotypes and biases perpetuated by media regarding career choices.

- **Community Perception:** Address external pressures, such as societal expectations or peer opinions. Encourage students to make informed decisions based on their own values.
7. **Long-Term Vision:**
- **Career Path Mapping:** Help students create a long-term vision for their careers. Encourage them to explore both stability and passion.
 - **Adaptability:** Prepare students for a dynamic job market. Careers evolve, and adaptability is crucial.

Compliance With Ethical Standards

Research ethics were strictly observed throughout the course of the conduct of this study. Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethical Committee of Foundation University Research Office. Moreover, informed consent was taken from each respondent included in the study before gathering any data from them. Prior to conducting this study, the researchers consulted 3 panels of experts for the necessary improvement of the research instrument that was utilized. During the study, the right to self-determination, confidentiality and anonymity, benefits, and risks of the study were observed and respected.

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